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The Effectiveness of Fresh Technique in Writing Descriptive Essay at Smpn 12 Gorontalo

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Abstract

Writing is one of the skills that must be possessed by students when learning English. It is one way of expressing ideas, feelings, thoughts, even arguments and knowledge into a piece of paper. Descriptive text is a text which purpose is to describe someone, a place, or something. FRESH Technique is a teaching technique can help student writing descriptive text. The aim of this study was to find out the significant difference in writing achievement before and after students taught using the FRESH technique in writing descriptive Essay. In conducting the study, The method in this study is a quantitative method. A-pre experimental was employed as research design conducted into one group. The sample of this study is the seventh-grade in class VII-3 The researcher took twenty five students as the sample. The instrument for collecting the data using T-test that included a pre-test and post-test. The data analysis using T-test and analyzed by using SPSS version 25. The research found that the students had an average developmental in writing descriptive essay of 10,44 on pre test and 15,4 on the post-test. The students writing development is 37,82%. This is supported by the larger t-test value showed that the t-test 29,632 > t-table 2,807. The result indicates that, the null hypothesis (H₀) was rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted it means that FRESH Technique can effective increased student's writing in descriptive essay.

Keywords : *Writing, Descriptive Text, FRESH Technique, Teaching writing.*

Abstrak

Menulis adalah salah satu keterampilan yang harus dimiliki oleh siswa ketika belajar bahasa Inggris. Ini adalah salah satu cara untuk mengekspresikan ide, perasaan, pikiran, bahkan argumen dan pengetahuan ke selembar kertas. Teks deskriptif adalah teks yang tujuannya adalah untuk menggambarkan seseorang, tempat, atau sesuatu. Teknik FRESH adalah teknik pengajaran yang dapat membantu siswa menulis teks deskriptif. Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk mengetahui perbedaan yang signifikan dalam prestasi menulis sebelum dan sesudah siswa diajarkan menggunakan teknik FRESH dalam menulis Esai deskriptif. Dalam melakukan penelitian, Metode dalam penelitian ini adalah metode kuantitatif. A-eksperimen awal digunakan sebagai desain penelitian yang dilakukan menjadi satu kelompok. Sampel penelitian ini adalah kelas tujuh di kelas VII-3 Peneliti mengambil dua puluh lima siswa sebagai sampel. Instrumen untuk mengumpulkan data menggunakan uji-T yang meliputi pre-test dan post-test. Analisis data menggunakan uji-T dan dianalisis dengan menggunakan SPSS versi 25. Penelitian ini menemukan bahwa siswa memiliki perkembangan rata-rata dalam menulis esai deskriptif sebesar 10,44 pada pre test dan 15,4 pada post-test. Perkembangan menulis siswa adalah 37,82%. Hal ini didukung oleh nilai uji-t yang lebih besar, yaitu 29,632 > 2,807. Hasil ini menunjukkan bahwa hipotesis nol (H₀) ditolak, sementara hipotesis alternatif (H_a) diterima. Ini berarti Teknik FRESH efektif meningkatkan kemampuan menulis siswa dalam esai deskriptif.

Kata Kunci: *Menulis, Teks Deskriptif, Teknik FRESH, Pengajaran menulis.*

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INTRODUCTION

Writing is one of the activities used by the writer to communicate with the reader. When the students have ideas or knowledge in their minds, they can use writing to express their ideas. Perhaps, the writer able to communicate and express their ideas with readers. According to A. D. Jayanti, (2019) writing is an expressive activity meaning that the learners can express their ideas and knowledge by putting them into written form. Perhaps, the learners can express their ideas effectively, convey their thoughts into good sentences, and put them in a writing form. The most difficult text to write for the students is descriptive text in the form of paragraph. This matter is caused by some cases. Most of the

students lacked vocabularies and also got difficulties to express their ideas in writing especially in English language.

One of the most crucial language skills to master is writing. Writing in a second language is challenging because it is one of the four fundamental skills that are extremely complex and challenging to learn. Student must be able to organize, convey, and develop their thoughts, feelings, or opinions in written language by following the writing process with the goal of being understood by the reader. The terms 'writing process' and writing strategy are a bit confusing in writing studies. Therefore, it is necessary to clarify this terminology at the outset study. Writing requires a process where the writer can explore and discover their thoughts and construct meaning. Writers usually go through a number of stages of development in writing. According to Flower and Hayes (1981), there are three stages of the writing process: planning (Planning), Drafting (Translating/Drafting), and Revision (Revising).

Writing to learn is a strategy that helps students think deeply about a text by activating background knowledge about a text, recording thinking while reading a text, and extending thinking about what was read. A writer's purpose is simply what it says on the tin. It's a consideration of what the author of a particular text was intending when they wrote it, and how they wanted their reader to feel when reading, or what reaction they wanted to encourage. Every text that's ever been written has a purpose. This means that children are likely to come across this topic regularly in their English lessons whether they're thinking about a text they are reading, or one they are writing themselves. Furthermore, the goal of writing is to (i) assist authors in "harvesting" their knowledge, (ii) to make the writers more confident and (iii) show them that writing can be a fulfilling and fruitful endeavor (Hairston, 1986).

Descriptive text is a text that describes or describes the shape, characteristics or properties of objects, animals, places, humans or certain special events. The opinion above, it can be concluded that the text contains a detailed description of an object, whether a living being, object, place, or event, so that the reader seems to see, hear, feel, or experience what the author describes himself. Descriptive writing can help student understanding for both readers and listeners. In addition Oshima and Hogue (2007) argue that it seen, felt and heard, must appear when writing a descriptive essay because the description helps the reader imagine the object being described by the writer.

According to Ermita et al (2019), descriptive writing aims to convey specific details about a particular item, which can be a person, thing, or place. As a result, the text might influence the reader's emotions and ideas about the five senses, such as hearing, feeling, smelling, seeing, and tasting. Teaching writing is not simple as teaching other language since it has conventional rules.

Knowing the stages of writing of process, the students are demanded to get the knowledge of how to write well. It is believed that writing is a kind of reflection of the writer's cognition since that writing will represent the writer. One of important aspect of teaching writing is understanding that writing is not just about producing text, but also about a thinking process that involves planning, organizing ideas, and revising. Therefore, teaching writing should include the development of critical and creative thinking skills in addition to the writing technique itself.

Teachers basically only provide topics without explaining how to write well, which can have an impact on the decline in students' writing skills in developing the ideas they want to write about. The efforts that can be made to overcome this problem are to apply the FRESH technique, which can be used to improve and enhance students' ability in descriptive essay.

According to Faisal (2010), people rely heavily on their knowledge of the subject matter when they write. The FRESH technique is one method that can be applied when teaching writing in the classroom. Fresh Technique is a technique in which each of its letter has own meaning. Fresh technique is a technique in which each of its letter has own meaning. "F" stands for "Fact". "Fact" means the identification of the object or it can be called general description of the object. Usually it contains object "s" name, kind of the object, etc. "R" stands for "Reason", it means a supporting idea that strengthen the fact. "E" stands for "Elaboration". Elaboration means the explanation of the reason. The teachers should elaborate it in detail, so the students can get clear description of the object. "SH" stands for "Shift", which can be meant decision or conclusion. It is the conclusion of the information before.

Previous researchers have stated that the FRESH Technique is effective improving students' writing skills of eight-grade students Ria N, (2019). Other studies mention FRESH Technique could improve students' competence in writing descriptive texts Faisal & Wulandari (2013). Subsequent researchers have also reported similar findings. Achmad, D. (2019) conducted a quantitative study of first-year high school students in Banda Aceh. This study used experimental techniques to measure the

effectiveness of the FRESH technique. The FRESH Technique can be used to improve students' writing skills, especially in writing descriptive texts.

Based on the results of previous studies, it can be concluded that the FRESH Technique is very effective in improving students' descriptive writing skills. However, previous studies have not used the FRESH Technique in seventh grade classes in Gorontalo. Therefore, this study will focus on how the effective FRESH Technique can improve students' descriptive writing skills using the FRESH Technique.

METHOD

In this research, the researcher made use of the quantitative research because the researcher wants to know the effectiveness of FRESH technique on teaching student's descriptive text writing. Creswell (2014) asserts that quantitative research examines the relationships between variables in order to test objective theories. This study was conducted at SMP 12 Gorontalo located on Jl. Lupoyo, Kota Utara District, Gorontalo City, during the academic year 2024/2025, totaling 80 students across three classes of first-year students.

From the population, the researcher takes one class as the sample of this research. The sample of this research was class VII.3. There are 25 students in this class. Those students in academic years of 2024/2025. For the sample in this study the researcher used purposive sampling. The researchers took this class as a sample because based on informal interview with the teacher, students' ability to write descriptive essay still had problems.

The research design used in this research was a pre-experimental design. This design consists of pre-test, treatment, and post-test. The research utilized a pre-experimental design, with pre-tests and post-tests administered to measure students' writing abilities before and after the application of the FRESH technique. According to Sugiyono (2006), pre-experimental design is the simplest form of research design. The research took place as quantitative one group pretest-posttest design. One group pre-test post-test design (Sugiyono, 2012.) described below:

O1 X O2

Explanation :

O1 : Pre-Test
X : Treatment
O2 : Post-Test

Instrument In this research the researcher used pretest and posttest. The writer gave pretest before the teaching learning process and give posttest after the teacher learning process has been completed. This measure the effectiveness of FRESH technique towards student ability in writing descriptive text. The researcher gave score and analyzed the student's ability in writing descriptive text based on the aspect of writing descriptive text.

To make them clearer, the research described them one by one, they are:

a. Pre-test

The pre-test used in this research is to know the student's writing ability in descriptive text before the teaching applying FRESH technique. The researcher distributed question sheets consist of 4 pictures and 1 number to students on November 5th, 2024.

b. Treatment

In this treatment, the researcher applied FRESH technique in enhancing students' ability and knowledge in writing descriptive writing. The treatment was conducted in six meetings from November 9 to November 26, 2024. Briefly all the treatments are treated same aspect and process but each meetings have different topic. The researcher giving an explanation of how to enhance students' ability and knowledge about writing descriptive text using FRESH Technique. Every meeting took about two hours and forty minutes. The research used Modul Ajar, power point and projector that provided by the school.

c. Post – test

The researcher gave the post-test to the students after the treatment for 6 meetings. The aim of post-test was to know the student ability in writing descriptive essay after they got treatment. The form

of the post-test was similar to the pre-test student can choose 1 picture that they want to describe. On November 30th, 2024, the researcher distributed the post-test.

The two variables of this research are independent and dependent variables, the portrait of two variables is as follows.

X = Independent variable is "FRESH Technique"

Y = Dependent Variable is "Student's writing ability in descriptive essay"

The data were collected from an essay test. This measures the effectiveness of FRESH Technique towards student ability in writing descriptive essays. The researcher gave scores and analyzed the student's ability in writing descriptive essays based on the aspect of writing descriptive text. The data of this research was analyzed quantitatively, meaning that the data analyzed by using numbers. Furthermore, the data of this research is analyzed statically following analysis will be scored by using an analytical scale for rating composition tasks developed by Brown (2007).

The researchers provide the highest score 4 in 5 components. In writing the text, the researcher gave five scores following: content, organization, grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics. The researcher gave 20 for each very good score. So the highest score is 100.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the researcher observed and measured the success of the FRESH Technique based on the criteria derived from the advantages of using the FRESH Technique, as stated by Faisal and Wulandari (2013). The following were the achievements and improvements of the students who experienced the advantages of using the FRESH Technique as stated by Faisal and Wulandari (2013) including:

- 1) FRESH Technique helps students organize their ideas step by step to get a clear, detailed, and fluent organization of a descriptive text. In this study, the researcher can see FRESH Technique helps students organize their ideas step by step by providing a clear structure that students can follow. First step, students can focus on the main topic that they want to describe. The second step, students can reflect by brainstorming specific details related to the topic such as characteristics, appearances, or emotions, for example, if the topic is "My Pet Cat" students can reflect by brainstorming details such as cats have soft white fur (appearance), their playful and friendly behavior (characteristics) and the happiness they feel when playing with the cat (emotions). The third step, students will explain the ideas in an organized way, and group the details together. The fourth step, students show their descriptions through vivid language and make their writing more detailed and interesting. The last step, students will highlight the most important points to ensure their text is clear, coherent, and fluent.
- 2) The element of FRESH can support learners to find what should be written first and next to get a fluent descriptive text so students are able to master the rule of how to write a good descriptive text. In this study, the researcher can see the improvement from the students in the learning process. There are differences in each meeting from students feeling confused to writing descriptive essays until the students are able to master the rule of how to write a good descriptive text in an essay.
- 3) The imagination given by FRESH technique can strengthen students' creativity because they can participate or interact actively. In this study, the researcher doesn't see an increase in imagination from students' work, but the researcher can see if the meeting can be more than six meetings or active engagement with each step of the FRESH Technique allows them to go beyond basic descriptions and produce rich, creative texts full of original ideas.
- 4) Simple and easy technique, FRESH Technique can make students easy to understand the material. In this study, the researcher can see the students understand easily and write in the correct way from the process of learning in each meeting.
- 5) In FRESH Technique, students can work individually or work together in a group. In this statement, the researcher does not really agree, because when the researcher uses FRESH Technique and asks students to work together in a group is not successful because not all students can work in a group.
- 6) Students can construct their own knowledge based on experience and FRESH Technique can support students' engagement in the writing process. In this study, the researcher can see how students' writing ability can change and improve when using FRESH Technique.

The Increase of Student Writing

Graph 1 The Increase of Student Writing

The implementation of the FRESH Technique resulted in a significant improvement in students' writing skills. The average score increased from 10.44 in the pre-test to 15.4 in the post-test, indicating a 37.82% gain on a 1–20 scale. As illustrated in Chart above, this increase demonstrates the effectiveness of the FRESH Technique in enhancing the writing performance of VII-3 grade students at SMPN 12 Gorontalo. The t-test value is greater than the t-table value. It showed that the t-test 29,632 > t-table 2,807 it means that students' writing increased after using FRESH Technique for VII-3 grade students of SMPN 12 Gorontalo.

Graph 1

Based on the bar graph above, From 1 number of question are divided into 5 aspects to assess students' writing in descriptive essay. The highest increasing was in the aspect of content and organization. The researcher explains the difference mean score between pretest and posttest as follows:

- Content increased from 2.52 to 3.52
- Organization increased from 2.48 to 3.24
- Vocabulary increased from 2 to 2.8
- Grammar increased from 1.8 to 2.92
- Mechanic increased from 1.64 to 2.92

Graph 3

Based the analysis of pre-test and post-test data revealed a significant improvement in students' writing performance.

In the pre-test, scores ranged from 35 to 70, with a mean score of 50.

In contrast, post-test scores ranged from 65 to 90, with a mean of 75.

These results indicate that students' writing skills improved after the implementation of the FRESH Technique in writing descriptive essays. Based on the result in the finding section, the mean score of the post-test was notably higher than that of the pre-test. This is indicating that students performed better after using FRESH Technique.

The researcher believed that from the difference score between pre-test and post-test prove that FRESH Technique effectively helped students to organize their ideas and express them clearly in written form. The success of FRESH Technique in increasing the students' achievement in writing descriptive essays can not be separated from some advantages which were stated by Faisal and Wulandari (2013).

FRESH Technique can help students organize their ideas step by step to get a clear, detailed and fluent organization of a descriptive text. Fact, Reason, Elaboration and Shift. This sequence guides students in developing their writing from a strong main idea to deeper details, personal connection, and reflection. It is also supported by Faisal and Wulandari (2013) who define FRESH Technique as a way of developing descriptive text's generic structure. As a result, students' descriptive texts become more organized, detailed, and fluent, making it easier to express thoughts clearly and logically. In instance, in FRESH Technique the students will follow some steps that make students easy in writing descriptive essays.

CONCLUSION

According to the results analysis of data findings and discussion, the researcher seeks a conclusion that FRESH Technique can help students to increase student writing skill in descriptive essays. This technique provides a clear structure and effective guidance for students in developing their ideas, so that their writing becomes more organized, detailed, and interesting. Moreover, based on the pre-test result, it showed that the students' ability in writing descriptive essays was still low. It is proved that from the students' pre-test score, which was the lowest score was 35 and the highest score was 70. After using FRESH Technique in the treatment process, the students' score was increased. It can be seen from the students' post-test score that the lowest score was 65 and the highest score was 90. As a result, the researcher concludes that the use of FRESH Technique in SMPN 12 Gorontalo for VII-3 grade students has a good impact and effectively increases student's writing skill in descriptive essays.

The researcher suggested for the teacher to use FRESH Technique because the technique's flexibility enables teachers to adjust the level of difficulty according to students' language proficiency and academic needs, making it an effective tool for enhancing writing skills in various educational contexts. The researcher also suggested to the future research to conduct an initial analysis of the writing ability level of students who are the subjects of the research. It is also important to understand students' difficulties related to writing descriptive text so that the implementation of the technique can be more relevant, and researchers really hope that there will be development of the FRESH Technique so that it is more suitable for use in other learning contexts in the future and can be beneficial for students in different grades or locations.

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